

NEID Status After the Fire

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It has been a busy year for NEID, the new extreme precision radial velocity (EPRV) spectrograph installed at the WIYN 3.5m Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory. After successfully passing an operational readiness review in summer 2021, NEID transitioned to full science operations in the 2021B semester. NEID had almost marked a year of full science operations when the Contreras Fire halted operations in June, and the instrument was warmed up to safely await the return of observatory infrastructure.

Figure 1. Members of the NEID Team (L to R: Danny Krolikowski, Steward Observatory, University of Arizona; Sarah Logsdon, WIYN/NEID Instrument Scientist; and Andy Monson, Steward Observatory, University of Arizona) prepare to pump down the NEID cryostat in October 2022. Credit: C. Bender/Steward Observatory/University of Arizona

The WIYN team and our NEID collaborators at the University of Arizona spent the summer and early fall checking NEID subsystems for functionality and cleaning the WIYN building, including the NEID clean room, from top to bottom. As soon as line power was restored to the summit in October, the team began pumping and cooling down the spectrograph in preparation for a return to science observing. In the meantime, a backup generator, which will strengthen the power systems infrastructure for uninterrupted operations, has also been added at WIYN, thanks to a Heising-Simons Foundation grant. Early, low-precision science observations resumed on 11 November, with high-precision science expected to follow shortly.

While work is ongoing to update the NEID pipeline and verify instrument performance, preliminary analysis indicates that NEID is performing as expected. The NEID team is thrilled to be restarting science operations and is looking forward to more cutting-edge EPRV data to come.

In the midst of our restart work, we also welcomed two new NEID Queue Observers, Pipa Fernandez and Yatrik Patel (Figures 2 and 3), who join Eli Golub and Jesus Higuera on the NEID observing team.

While we have been busy at Kitt Peak bringing NEID back on line, NEID PIs have been working hard analyzing and publishing their NEID data. To date, 11 peer-reviewed papers using NEID data have been published in 2022, with more papers under review or close to submission. The published papers include the recent ‘Marshmallow’ world paper by Shubham Kanodia et al. (2022, AJ, 164, 81), which used both NEID and NESSI (WIYN’s speckle imager) to help characterize the lowest-density Jupiter-like planet orbiting a cool red dwarf star known to date.

Figure 2. NEID queue observer Pipa Fernandez. Credit: J. Higuera/NOIRLab

Figure 3. NEID queue observer Yatrik Patel. Credit: S. Logsdon/NOIRLab